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Executive Summary

The epigenome is at the interface between intrinsic (genetic) and external (environmental) factors influencing cellular behaviour. DNA methylation, defined as the addition of methyl groups on the C5 position of cytosines on the DNA in the context of CpGs, is a key part of the epigenome which integrates these intrinsic and external factors and records them as a signature on the DNA. DNA methylation is also influenced by cellular ageing and forms the basis of several existing “epigenetic clocks” which utilise a combination of age-associated differentially methylated positions to predict chronological age. Many age-related DNA methylation changes are common across most tissue types. Whether discordant tick rates between cell type-specific and general epigenetic clocks play a role in health or disease has remained largely unexplored. Recently we reported that cervical samples, consisting of a mixture of hormone-sensitive epithelial and immune cells, are a suitable surrogate tissue for prediction of breast cancer and may reflect systemic epigenetic programming defects. We therefore aimed to investigate if cell type-specific ageing signatures in cervical samples are associated with breast cancer risk.

Using DNA methylation analysis of cervical samples, we developed the WID (Women’s cancer risk IDentification) general clock, shared by both epithelial and immune cells and optimised for cervical samples. Surprisingly, the WID general clock outperforms two commonly used epigenetic clocks for age prediction in several tissues. Via computational inference of sample composition, we also identified epithelial- and immune-specific epigenetic clocks. A discordance between WID-general and epithelial age (WID-relative-epithelial-age, WID-REA) in cervical samples is associated with breast cancer. The same effect is observed in breast tissue from individuals at increased risk of breast cancer (*BRCA1/2* mutation carriers) but could be rescued via risk-reducing pharmacological intervention in a clinical study. Interestingly, the WID-REA also differs between women who received hormone replacement therapy (HRT) and did or did not develop breast cancer, indicating a potential to monitor individual breast cancer risk on HRT using the WID-REA.

We therefore provide novel general and tissue-specific epigenetic clocks which are accurate at predicting chronological age and may further be an informatic measure of disease risk.

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1 Introduction

Ageing has previously been described to be associated with distinct cellular changes including telomere shortening and DNA methylation (DNAm) alterations. DNAm changes form the basis of so-called epigenetic clocks which can be used to predict chronological age¹⁻⁴. Most available epigenetic clocks are designed to represent tissue-independent predictors of age and utilise common sample types such as blood or saliva samples^{1,5}.

The “tick rate” of epigenetic clocks may allow for the prediction of disease and mortality risk⁶. Both the number of cell divisions and replication-independent factors determine the pace of epigenetic clocks; hence, in order to use an epigenetic clock as a surrogate marker to monitor disease risk in a cell type as well as conditions which impact on this cell type must be considered. This is particularly crucial for multifactorial diseases like cancer where hormonal exposure is crucially involved and cell division may be limited to cells that are hormone receptor positive, including most breast cancers. For these diseases, cell type-specific epigenetic clocks that mirror the cells at risk may be of use (i.e., hormone-sensitive epithelial cells), but these cells are lacking from blood or saliva samples. Conversely, cervical samples, routinely obtained from women aged 25-64 years, are a source of hormone-sensitive epithelial and immune cells that could help to define epigenetic clocks indicating disease risk. Whether specific epigenetic clocks in cervical samples or a discordance in tick rates between general and cell type-specific epigenetic clocks could predict disease remained unknown.

As part of Deliverable D8.2 we aimed to define:

- an optimised “general epigenetic clock” – i.e., a list of CpGs – which collectively change with age in cervical samples.
- cell type-specific epigenetic clocks for epithelial and immune cells within cervical samples.

We analysed cervical liquid-based cytology samples and describe novel epigenetic clocks, the Women’s cancer risk IDentification clocks, which can indicate cancer risk and are altered upon hormone exposure.

2 Methods

2.1 Samples

Samples used for development of the general and cell type-specific clocks were collected as part of the FORECEE Programme, a European research project aimed at developing new strategies for female cancer prediction (Table 1). Cervical screening was performed for women aged >18 years across five different European locations, including the Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Norway, and the UK. FORECEE has received ethical approval from the UK Health Research Authority (REC 14/LO/1633) and other contributing centres. Women with either breast, ovarian, or endometrial cancer as well as age-matched controls were included.

Table 1. Samples in the FORECEE Study used for training and validation.

SET	TYPE	NUMBER OF SAMPLES
TRAINING	Control	869
VALIDATION	Control	225
	Breast cancer	442
	Ovarian cancer	289

Cervical smears were collected with a Rovers cervical brush and stored in PreservCyt solution (ThinPrep). DNA was extracted from cervical samples on a Hamilton Star liquid handling platform using the Nucleo-Mag Blood 200 μ L kit (Macherey Nagel, cat #744501.4) with prior modifications for optimal lysis of cervical cell pellets. Concentration and quality absorbance ratios were measured using a Nanodrop-8000 (Thermo Scientific) and extracted DNA was stored at -80°C until further analysis.

2.2 DNA extraction and methylation analysis

DNA normalised to 25 ng/ μ L and 500 ng total DNA were bisulfite modified using the EZ-96 DNA Methylation-Lightning kit (Zymo Research Corp, cat #D5047) on the Hamilton Star Liquid handling platform. 8 μ L of modified DNA were subjected to methylation analysis on the Illumina InfiniumMethylation EPIC BeadChip (Illumina, CA, USA) at UCL Genomics according to the manufacturer's standard protocol.

2.3 Methylation data processing

All methylation microarray data were processed through the same standardised pipeline. Raw data was loaded using the R package minfi. Any samples with median methylated and unmethylated intensities > 9.5 were removed. Any probes with a detection p-value < 0.01 were regarded

as failed. Any samples with > 10% failed probes, and any probes with > 10% failure rate were removed from the dataset. Beta values from failed probes (approximately 0.001% of the dataset) were imputed using the `impute.knn` function as part of the `impute` R package.

Non-CpG probes (2,932), SNP-related probes as identified by Zhou et al., and chrY probes were removed from the dataset. An additional 6,102 previously identified probes that followed a trimodal methylation pattern characteristic of an underlying SNP were removed.

Background intensity correction and dye bias correction was performed using the `minfi` single sample `preprocessNoob` function. Probe bias correction was performed using the beta mixture quantile normalisation (BMIQ) algorithm. Sample composition (immune cell, epithelial cell) was inferred using the EpiDISH algorithm.

2.4 Epigenetic clock development

The R package `glmnet` with $\alpha = 1$ (lasso penalty) was used to train a regression model to predict chronological age as the output. Beta-values from the 776,725 CpGs in the training set were used as inputs to the model. Ten-fold cross-validation was utilised to determine the optimal value of the regularisation parameter λ . The final model included non-zero weights for $n=759$ CpG sites. Denoting the beta values as β_1, \dots, β_n and the regression coefficients from the trained model as w_1, \dots, w_n ,

then the WID general clock is given $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \beta_i + \text{intercept}$, where the intercept term was also fitted during the model training phase.

In order to identify epithelial- and immune-specific age-associated changes at each CpG site, we fitted the following linear model. At a given CpG site let β denote the beta-value, ic and ec denote the immune and epithelial proportions, and age denote chronological age. We linearly regressed β on ic , ec , age , $ic \cdot age$, and $ec \cdot age$. Coefficients corresponding to the interaction terms capture cell-type specific associations between beta values and chronological age. The linear regression model was applied to all 776,725 CpGs in the training set.

Epithelial-specific CpGs were identified by selecting CpGs with an absolute epithelial-specific coefficient $>10^{-3}$ and an absolute immune-specific coefficient $<10^{-5}$ (168 in total). Similarly, immune-specific CpGs were identified by selecting CpGs with an absolute immune-specific coefficient $>10^{-3}$ and an absolute epithelial-specific coefficient $<10^{-5}$ (56 in total). The WID epithelial clock was trained on the epithelial-specific CpGs by using

ridge regression to predict chronological age using β and $\beta \cdot ic$ interaction terms as inputs. Interaction terms were included to accommodate any cell-type specific dependencies. The final clock was defined as

$\sum_{i=1}^{168} w_i^1 \beta_i + w_i^2 \beta_i ic_i + intercept$. Similarly the WID immune clock was defined

as $\sum_{i=1}^{56} w_i^1 \beta_i + w_i^2 \beta_i ic_i + intercept$.

The WID-relative-epithelial-age (REA) was defined as WID epithelial clock – WID general clock, and the WID-relative-immune-age was defined as WID immune clock – WID general clock.

2.5 Epigenetic clock validation datasets

Epigenetic clocks were validated in an independent validation set (part of the FORECEE study, Table 1).

Additionally, we tested epigenetic clock performance in a variety of tissues using publicly available datasets obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) (Table 2).

Table 2. GEO samples used for validation.

TISSUE	DATASET	NUMBER OF SAMPLES
FAT	GSE131461	20
BLOOD	GSE131461	20
	GSE145254	23
	GSE143307	48
	GSE130748	19
	GSE123914	69
MUSCLE	GSE114763	9
COLON	GSE142257	31
BUCCAL	GSE157252	134
SKIN	GSE151617	16
BRAIN	GSE138597	12
BONE	GSE138307	29

3 Results

3.1 General epigenetic clock

We identified age-associated differentially methylated positions in cervical samples from 869 healthy women (training dataset) and developed the WID general clock (Women's cancer risk identification), a linear combination of n=759 CpG sites. The performance was evaluated in an

independent validation set consisting of 225 cervical cytology samples from healthy women (Figure 1). The error, defined as the median absolute difference between true and predicted age, was 2.4 years and the Pearson correlation was 0.95 ($p < 10^{-16}$). Consistent with previous reports in the literature, we observed a slight underestimation of age in older individuals

Figure 1. The WID general clock, calculated using a combination of 759 CpGs, is highly correlated with chronological age.

The WID general clock offered substantially superior performance in cervical samples in comparison to the most frequently quoted clocks previously published (Figure 2)^{1,2}. This was expected as our clock was optimised for cervical cytology specimens. Comparing the three clocks side by side in fat, blood, muscle, colon, saliva, breast, skin, brain, buccal, and bone samples we found that the WID general clock offers more accurate age prediction in all but brain and bone tissues. Therefore, the WID general clock represents a novel accurate clock for age prediction for a variety of tissues.

Figure 2. The WID general clock offers superior chronological age prediction in most tissues, except brain and bone, compared to the Horvath and Hannum epigenetic clocks. **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$ in Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

3.2 Cell type-specific epigenetic clocks

The WID general clock is optimised for heterogeneous samples and as a consequence is largely based on CpGs that vary in both epithelial and immune cells. We hypothesised that the WID general clock defines a shared tick rate that is present across all cell types in cervical cytology samples. To develop cell type-specific clocks in cervical samples, we applied a linear model to each of the 776,725 CpGs in our training set and identified 168 epithelial-specific and 56 immune specific age-associated differentially methylated positions (DMPs). These were defined as CpGs with an absolute epithelial-specific coefficient $> 10^{-3}$ and absolute immune-specific coefficient $< 10^{-5}$ or vice versa. Using ridge regression on these CpGs, we derived the WID epithelial and WID immune clock. Both clocks are defined by a linear combination of beta values and beta-proportion interaction terms to account for any dependence on immune cell proportion. The epithelial and immune clocks had errors of 6.3 and 7.6 years respectively, which was poorer than the cell type-independent clock (Figure 3).

Figure 3. WID epithelial and immune clocks correlate less well with chronological age.

We were particularly interested in the discordance between general and specific clocks. Cervical epithelial cells are steroid hormone-sensitive (e.g., oestrogen and progesterone). Menopause, which occurs at around 50 years of age, leads to dramatically decreased levels of steroid hormones and there was a significant change in the general and epithelial clock after menopause (Figure 4), suggesting that the clocks are influenced by hormonal changes occurring at menopause.

Figure 4. The WID general and epithelial clocks are altered by menopause. *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$, in Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

3.3 Relative epithelial age

The WID epithelial and immune clocks are derived from age DMPs specific to epithelial and immune cells but as they are a linear combination of beta values, they define epigenetic clocks in any cell. We can therefore interpret each cell as possessing three separate epigenetic clocks – general, epithelial, and immune. The tick rate of each clock is cell type-specific; the general clock serves as a good predictor of age across all cell types whereas the epithelial clock acts as a better predictor in epithelial cells etc.

Examining the general, epithelial, and immune clocks in pre-menopausal women we observed a slightly increased general tick rate and a reduced epithelial tick rate in breast and ovarian cancers. This motivated us to define the WID-relative epithelial age (WID-REA), i.e., the difference between epithelial and general clocks. The WID-REA in pre-menopausal breast cancers was significantly lower than in samples from healthy cancer-free controls (Figure 5), and women in the lowest quartile had a breast cancer odds ratio of 2.7 (data not shown). A reduced WID-REA was also present in pre-menopausal ovarian cancers but not statistically significant.

Figure 5. The WID-REA is reduced in pre-menopausal women with breast cancer. **, $p < 0.01$ in Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

Hormones are another factor that may influence epithelial age, and therefore we examined the WID-REA with respect to hormone replacement therapy (HRT). Post-menopausal cancer-free control women who were ever on HRT showed a significantly reduced WID-REA (Figure 6a), and the reduction increased with HRT duration (Figure 6b), consistent with a retardation of the epithelial clock relative to the general clock that becomes more pronounced over time. Surprisingly, HRT had no effect whatsoever on the WID-REA in post-menopausal women with breast or ovarian cancer (Figure 6c, d). Therefore, our data suggest that the implication of a negative WID-REA is strongly dependent on menopausal status: in pre-menopausal women, a negative WID-REA is associated with increased cancer risk, whereas in a post-menopausal context the directionality is reversed.

Figure 6. The impact of HRT on the WID-REA. Post-menopausal controls who received HRT showed a significantly reduced WID-REA compared to those who did not (a), and the effect was time-dependent (b). Conversely, women with breast (c) or ovarian cancer (d) did not show this effect. *, $p < 0.05$; **, $p < 0.01$, in Wilcoxon signed-rank test.

3.4 WID clocks R package

To enable research use of the above WID clocks, we have generated an R package which allows for calculation of the WID clocks from methylation array data. The package is freely available on github ⁸.

4 Summary

Here, we describe the development of novel epigenetic clocks which are both tissue-independent and highly accurate predictors of chronological

age (WID general clock) and cell type-specific, potentially reflecting disease risk. Additionally, we have generated an R package to make our epigenetic clocks available for research use ⁸.

5 References

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